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Modeling for predicting the thermal protective and comfort performance of fabrics used in firefighters' clothing

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Introduction

Standardized test methods are available for measuring the thermal protective as well as comfort performance of fabrics used in firefighters' clothing. However, these tests are usually fabric destructive in nature, time consuming, and/or expensive to carry out on a regular basis. To overcome these limitations, empirical Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) and/or Artificial Neural Network (ANN) models have been developed to accurately predict the thermal protective performance from a set of fabric properties under different heat exposures (e.g., flame, radiant-heat) and intensities faced by on-duty firefighters in a fire hazard [1, 2]. Altogether, it has been found that ANN models predict the protective performance more accurately than MLR models. However, these are separate ANN models for different heat exposures of different intensities; so, the universal application of these ANN models together highly increases the complexity of the prediction, comparability, and/or holistic understanding of the actual thermal protective performance of a fabric under a representative working scenario of firefighters. Hence, a model is required to measure and holistically understand the thermal protective performance of fabrics under a heat exposure and intensity that simulates representative firefighters' working scenario. Furthermore, no empirical model such as MLR or ANN is available to date for conveniently predicting the comfort performance of fabrics.

In this study, thermal protective performance of a set of fabrics was measured under flame and radiant-heat exposures at different intensities using standardized test methods. And, comfort performance of the fabrics was also measured using the standard sweating guarded torso test and a statistical model. As a first objective of this study, a standard representative test method with a particular heat exposure and intensity was needed to be identified that can holistically measure the protective performance of the fabrics (in a representative working scenario of firefighters) for further modeling. Next, the key fabric properties that affect the thermal protective and comfort performances were identified. By employing these key fabric properties, MLR and ANN models were developed to predict the thermal protective and comfort performances. Finally, two better-fitting high-performance models were identified for predicting the thermal protective as well as comfort performances.

Methods

For this study, 6 single- and 13 multi-layered fabrics that are commercially used to manufacture firefighters' protective clothing were selected. The fundamental properties of these fabrics (weight, thickness, thermal resistance, air permeability, evaporative resistance, and water spreading speed) were measured using the standard test methods developed by International Organization for Standardization (ISO) or American Association of Textile Chemists and Colorists (AATCC). Thermal protective performance values of the selected fabrics were measured by ISO test methods under intensified heat exposures usually faced by firefighters in a fire hazard (10 kW/m² radiant-heat, 40 kW/m² radiant-heat, and 80 kW/m² flame). By comparing these values, a standard representative test method with a particular heat exposure and intensity was identified that can holistically measure and classify the protective performance of the fabrics for further modeling. Comfort performance of the fabrics was determined by ISO 18640-1:2018 test method and a statistical model.

In this study, two types of empirical modeling methodologies i.e., MLR and ANN, were used for predicting the thermal protective and comfort performances of fabrics. The MLR is a statistical modeling tool that represents a linear relationship equation between the independent input (key fabric properties) and dependent output (thermal protective or thermo-physiological comfort performance) variables. The ANN is

a powerful data modeling tool that could capture and represent any kind of relationship between the input and output variables. This study employed a three-layered (input layer, one hidden layer, and output layer) feed-forward (one of the specialized versions of feedforward network i.e., fitnet) backpropagation (Levenberg-Marquardt backpropagation method) ANN model for predicting the protective and comfort performances. Above-mentioned fabric properties were used as independent input variables for predicting the output variable (e.g., thermal protective performance, comfort performance). Contextually, it is notable that too many and/or mutually dependent input variables (e.g., fabric properties) could lead to the error in predicting the output variable. Therefore, the key fabric properties for protective and comfort performances were identified and used as input variables. The MLR and ANN models developed were further compared based on their predicting performance parameters [Coefficient of Determination (R^2), Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), and p-value] to identify the better-fitting high-performance models to predict the thermal protective and comfort performances. During the comparison, a model with high R^2 , low RMSE, and p-values of <0.05 was inferred as the better-fitting high-performance model.

Results and Discussion

It has been found that thermal protective performances of fabrics under heat exposures of different intensities (10 kW/m² radiant-heat, 40 kW/m² radiant-heat, and 80 kW/m² flame) are linearly correlated. This suggests that the heat absorption and degradation energy generated by the fabrics are comparable under all of these heat exposures and intensities. As the flame exposure comprehensively simulates the combined effect of flame, radiant-heat, and hot gasses instead of only radiant-heat, this exposure was chosen to measure and model the thermal protective performance of fabrics.

It has been found that thermal resistance and evaporative resistance are the key fabric properties to directly affecting the thermal protective performance. Also, weight and evaporative resistance were identified as the key fabric properties to inversely affect the comfort performance; whereas, water spreading speed of the fabric that is in contact with the wearers' skin was identified as the key fabric property to directly affect the comfort performance. As per the finding from this study, ANN models are recommended to use for more accurately predicting the thermal protective and comfort performances from the key fabric properties.

Conclusions

This study clearly found that thermal resistance and evaporative resistance are positively related to the thermal protective performance; whereas, these two resistance properties are negatively related to the comfort performance of the fabrics. As the impact of different fabric properties (e.g., thermal resistance and evaporative resistance) is different for thermal protective and comfort performances, the need for an optimal balance between the thermal protective and comfort performances by controlling the fabric properties is required. In consideration with fabric properties, it is recommended to conduct a study about categorizing the existing fabrics based on the thermal protective and comfort performances to decide their suitability in different applications.

Additionally, the developed ANN models could be improved by considering the moistened fabrics and microclimate air gaps existing in between the fabric of clothing and firefighters' bodies. This is because firefighters sweat profusely on the fire ground due to the heat exposures and high physical activities involved in firefighting; this results in moisture accumulation inside the fabrics, which substantially affects the thermal protective and comfort performances, depending upon the size of the microclimate air gaps. This modeling study could also be realistically extended for predicting the thermal protective and comfort performance of whole clothing instead of only fabrics. This proposed modeling study could provide some insights into the impact of clothing features (fit, size, closures) on the thermal protective and comfort performances.

References

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